

EFFECT OF FOLIAR APPLICATION OF DIFFERENT VOLUMES OF NANO NITROGEN ON GROWTH AND YIELD OF MULBERRY

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Abstract

The effect of foliar application of different volumes of nano nitrogen on growth and yield of v-1 mulberry was studied. Ten treatments were laid out in RCBD with three replications, which consisted of different volumes of nano nitrogen fertilizer through foliar spray on 25 Days After Pruning. The significantly highest growth parameters on 30, 45 and 60 Days After Pruning viz., shoot length (43.53, 84.63 and 141.25 cm respectively), number of branches per plant (19.13, 21.17 and 22.66 No., respectively), number of leaves per plant (226.73, 602.83 and 752.83 No., respectively) and single leaf area (90.78, 119.81 and 126.40 cm², respectively) were recorded in mulberry plants raised with foliar application of 0.4 per cent nano nitrogen fertilizers at 225 ltr per acre on 25 DAP + 50 per cent nitrogen through soil application which was on par with 0.4 per cent nano nitrogen fertilizers at 200 ltr per acre on 25 DAP + 50 per cent nitrogen through soil application shoot length (43.46, 84.46 and 141.21 cm, respectively), number of branches per plant (18.9, 20.77 and 22.28 No., respectively), number of leaves per plant (220.89, 589.25 and 739.25 No., respectively) and single leaf area (90.64, 119.07 and 125.29 cm², respectively). The leaf yield (714.64 and 980.59 g /plant on 45 and 60 DAP, respectively) was maximum in the mulberry leaves sprayed with 0.4 per cent nano nitrogen at 225 ltr per acre on 25 DAP + 50 per cent soil application of nitrogen which was on par with leaf yield (697.33 and 956.83 g /plant on 45 and 60 DAP, respectively) mulberry leaves sprayed with 0.4 per cent nano nitrogen at 200 ltr per acre on 25 DAP + 50 per cent soil application of nitrogen.

Keywords : Nano nitrogen, Mulberry, growth, development.

Introduction

Mulberry is a fast growing, perennial, deep-rooted and foliage yielding deciduous woody tree species of Moraceae family. It is basically recognized as the main food source for silkworm, *Bombyx mori* L. Mulberry is unique as it is grown in India under different agro-climate conditions that range from temperate to tropical with broad geological distribution across the continent. The healthy growth, development and expression of economic traits by silkworms are largely influenced by the nutritional status of mulberry leaves.

Nitrogen is one of the key nutrients in cultivation of mulberry and to provide required nutrition to silkworm as silk being primarily comprised of different amino acids. It is an important component of many important structural, genetic and metabolic compounds in plant cells such as DNA and energy-transfer compounds (ATP), major component of chlorophyll, amino acids and proteins. Nitrogen exists in three general forms - organic nitrogen compounds, ammonium (NH₄⁺) ions and nitrate (NO₃⁻) ions which are available for plant. Nitrogen is also a primary building block for plant protoplasm that is needed for quick shoot growth and it is the important nutrient that normally produces greatest yield response in crop plants promoting rapid vegetative growth.

Fertilizer consumption pattern of India, recorded increasing trends in the use of conventional fertilizers (N, P₂O₅, K₂O and total NPK viz., 18863, 7984, 3740 and 28969 MT, respectively) by the farmers. From many years the synthetic or synthesized chemical fertilizers are still widely used, viz., Urea, Single Super Phosphate, Muriate of Potash, etc. for quick uptake of nutrient and to get instant results in plant growth and yield by farmers. Hence, the farmers are moving towards conventional fertilizers.

Approximately, 40-50 MT of foliage is removed from one hectare of mulberry garden annually every year. Plants are capable of

rejuvenating the foliage shortly by devouring soil nutrients that causes depletion of nutrients in soil and an annual input of 350:140:140 kg per ha of chemical fertilizer is applied. Continuous use of chemical fertilizer pollutes the soil and ground water by leaching of nutrients which results in alteration of chemical properties of soil viz., pH, EC, OC and less availability of nutrients to the plants. (Sakthivel *et al.*, 2018).

Most of the nitrogen is not available for plant completely due to leaching. Plant leaves are the main part in the plant system and direct application of fertilizer solution that contain nutrient helps in better absorption of nutrients and deficiencies can be corrected very quickly. Mulberry as a foliage crop responds well to timely application of nutrients through foliar sprays (Geetha, 2019). Foliar nutrition plays important role in the better growth, yield and biochemical constituents of mulberry leaves and also in superior quality of silk (Dhiraj and Kumar, 2012).

Nano-particles can be utilized as fertilizer for efficient nutrient management which are more eco-friendly and reduce environmental pollution, which are developed with the help of nanotechnology can be implemented in agriculture production system (Meena *et al.*, 2017). However, there is no recommended volume of fertilizer application for mulberry through foliar application of nano nitrogen hence, the present work is planned to study the effect of foliar application of different volumes of nano nitrogen on growth and yield of mulberry.

Materials and Methods

A field experiment was conducted during 2021-22 in well established Victory-1 (V-1) mulberry garden with spacing of (90 x 60 cm) at Department of Sericulture, UAS, GKVK, Bengaluru-65. The experiment was laid out in RCBD with 10 treatments, each treatment replicated thrice. The treatment details are given below.

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|----------------|--|
| T ₁ | : Foliar application of 0.4 % nano N at 150 ltr per acre+50 % N soil application |
| T ₂ | : Foliar application of 0.4 % nano N at 175 ltr per acre+50 % N soil application |
| T ₃ | : Foliar application of 0.4 % nano N at 200 ltr per acre+50 % N soil application |
| T ₄ | : Foliar application of 0.4 % nano N at 225 ltr per acre+50 % N soil application |
| T ₅ | : Foliar application of 2 % urea at 150 ltr per acre+50 % N soil application |
| T ₆ | : Foliar application of 2 % urea at 175 ltr per acre+50 % N soil application |
| T ₇ | : Foliar application of 2 % urea at 200 ltr per acre+ 50 % N soil application |
| T ₈ | : Foliar application of 2 % urea at 225 ltr per acre+50 % N soil application |
| T ₉ | : Control (Recommended PoP) |

T₁₀ : Absolute Control

Note:The above-mentioned treatments were given on 25th day after pruning and 100 per cent P & K along with Farm yard manure were applied commonly through soil application for all the treatments except absolute control.

PoP: Package of Practice

Results and Discussion

The observations of V-1 mulberry were recorded on growth parameters on 30, 45 and 60 DAP and yield parameters on 45 and 60 DAP. Foliar application of different volumes of nano nitrogen fertilizer had significant influence on growth and yield of V-1 mulberry variety.

Growth parameters

Maximum shoot length: Shoot length of mulberry was influenced by the foliar application of different volumes of nano nitrogen fertilizer (Table 1). The shoot length recorded on 30th, 45th and 60th day after pruning differed significantly with the foliar application of different volumes of nano nitrogen fertilizer.

Shoot length of mulberry differed significantly at different stages of pruning with different treatments and it increased progressively as it advanced. The treatment which received foliar application of 0.4 % nano N at 225 ltr per acre (T₄) recorded significantly highest shoot length of 43.53, 84.63 and 141.25 cm on 30th, 45th and 60th DAP, respectively, which was on par with 200 ltr per acre T₃ (43.46, 84.46 and 141.21 cm on 30th, 45th and 60th DAP, respectively) followed by 175 ltr per acre (T₂) 42.64, 82.68 and 131.33 cm on 30th, 45th and 60th DAP, respectively compared to control (T₉) 39.10, 76.37 and 120.07 cm on 30th, 45th and 60th DAP. Whereas, lowest shoot length (30.49, 65.49 and 105.30 cm, respectively) was recorded in T₁₀ (Absolute control).

Nano-fertilizers can easily penetrate into the leaves and facilitate by enhancing the availability of nutrients in the plants which results in healthy and vigorous plant growth (Meena *et al.*, 2017). However, nano-fertilizers are capable of holding abundance of nutrients due to their larger surface area, and release them slowly and steadily that facilitates uptake of nutrients matching the crop requirement without any ill-effects (Preetha and Balakrishnan, 2017).

Number of branches per plant: The number of shoots per plant differed significantly at different days after pruning with different treatment combinations (Table 2). On 30 DAP significantly highest number of branches per plant was noticed in 0.4 per cent nano N at 225 ltr per acre (T₄) (19.13) which was on par with 0.4 per cent nano N at 200 ltr per acre (T₃) (18.97) followed by 175 ltr per acre (T₂) (18.58) compared to control (T₉) (16.10), and the lowest number of branches per plant were recorded in absolute control (T₁₀) (14.73). Similarly on 45th DAP significantly highest number of branches per plant was observed in (T₄) (21.17) which was on par with T₃ (20.77) followed by T₂ (20.00) and the lowest number of branches per plant were recorded in absolute control T₁₀ (14.83). Significantly highest number of branches per plant was recorded on 60 DAP, from the mulberry plants sprayed with T₄ (22.66) which was on par with T₃ (22.28) followed by T₂ (21.61) compared to control T₉ (18.32) and lowest number of branches per plant was recorded in absolute control plot (T₁₀) (15.70).

Number of leaves per plant: The number of leaves per plant differed significantly at different days after pruning of mulberry with different treatments combinations (Table 3). On 30 DAP significantly highest number of leaves per plant was noticed in 0.4 per cent nano N at 225 ltr per acre (T₄) (226.73) which was on par with 0.4% nano N at 200 ltr per acre (T₃) (220.89) followed by 175 ltr per acre (T₂) (197.59) compared to control (T₉) (121.15) and the lowest number of leaves per plant were recorded in absolute control (T₁₀) (86.87).

Similarly, on 45th DAP, significantly highest number of leaves per plant were observed in T₄ (602.83) which was on par with T₃ (589.25) followed by T₂ (527.55) compared to control T₉ (479.72) and the

lowest number of leaves per plant was recorded in absolute control T₁₀ (234.90). Significantly highest number of leaves per plant were recorded (609.27) on 60th DAP from the mulberry plants sprayed with T₄ which were on par with T₃ (592.88) followed by T₂ (525.90) compared to T₉ (242.12) which is control plot and lowest number of leaves per plant were recorded in absolute control plot (T₁₀) (242.99). Increase in number of leaves is attributed mainly due to application of nano nitrogen compared to the treatments without nano fertilizers. Nitrogen contributes to absorb and assimilate more amount of nutrients for plant growth and development, quality being required for chlorophyll and enzyme synthesis.

Leaf area (cm²): Significant differences on the leaf area of different treatments were observed (Table 4). On 30th DAP significantly maximum single leaf area was noticed in 0.4 per cent nano N spray at 225 ltr per acre (T₄) (90.78) which was on par with 0.4 per cent nano N spray at 200 ltr per acre (T₃) (90.64) followed by 175 ltr per acre (T₂) (88.05) compared to control (T₉) (79.91) and the minimum single leaf area was recorded in absolute control (T₁₀) (77.91).

Subsequently on 45th DAP significantly maximum single leaf area was observed in T₄ (119.81) and which was on par with (T₃) (119.07) followed by (T₂) (115.59) and the minimum single leaf area was recorded in absolute control (T₁₀) (91.00). Significantly maximum single leaf area was recorded (126.40) on 60th DAP, from the mulberry plants receiving T₄ treatment which was on par with T₃ (125.29) followed by T₂ (123.15) compared to control T₉ (110.10) and minimum single leaf area was recorded in absolute control plot T₁₀ (92.94).

Improvement in the leaf area of plants receiving foliar application of different volumes of nanonitrogen fertilizer was due to ability of nanofertilizers in increasing the availability of nutrients by efficiently penetrating the leaves in the plant and also enhancing the stomatal size and frequency (Meena *et al.*, 2017).

Yield parameters of mulberry: A significant difference on leaf yield at different days after pruning as influenced by foliar spray of different volumes of nanonitrogen to mulberry (Table 5). Among different treatments, the leaf yield (714.64 g / plant, 6616.82 kg / ha / crop and 33.08 t / ha / yr) recorded on 45th DAP was significantly maximum in T₄ which was on par with T₃ (697.33 g / plant, 6456.55 kg / ha / crop and 32.28 t / ha / yr) followed by T₂ (669.99 g / plant, 6203.44 kg / ha / crop and 31.02 t / ha / yr) and T₁ (663.19 g / plant, 6140.43 kg / ha / crop and 30.70 t / ha / yr) compared to control (530.33 g / plant, 5880.33 kg / ha / crop and 29.40 t / ha / yr) and the lowest leaf yield was recorded in absolute control plot (T₁₀) (372.14 g / plant, 3445.64 kg / ha / crop and 17.23 t / ha / yr) on 45 day after pruning.

Among different treatments, the leaf yield (980.59 g / plant, 9079.31 kg / ha / crop and 45.40 t / ha / yr) recorded on 60th DAP was significantly highest in T₄ which was on par with T₃ (956.83 g / plant, 8859.32 kg / ha / crop and 44.30 t / ha / yr) followed by T₂ (920.43 g / plant, 8522.29 kg / ha / crop and 42.61 t / ha / yr) and T₁ (886.27 g / plant, 8205.97 kg / ha / crop and 30.70 t / ha / yr) compared to control T₉ (799.48 g / plant, 7402.39 kg / ha / crop and 37.01 t / ha / yr). The lowest leaf yield was recorded in absolute control plot (T₁₀) (482.55 g / plant, 4467.90 kg / ha / crop and 22.34 t / ha / yr) on 60th day after pruning.

Increase in the leaf yield might be due to higher plant height with more number of shoots and leaves per plant and more leaf area which can be attributed to the adequate supply of nitrogen in the leaves when sprayed with nano nitrogen particles, as the nanoparticles get into plant cells through either stomatal or vascular system. The mechanism of foliar uptake pathway for nanoparticles was well discussed by Eichert *et al.* (2008) and the stomatal pathway is highly capacitive because of its large size exclusion limit and its high transport velocity. These scientific reports support the present

hypothesis of nanoparticle penetration into plant cell through stomatal opening and natural nanopore which may have enhanced plant cell metabolic activities that lead to higher leaf yield.

An experiment on application of different levels of nitrogen nano-fertilizer through foliar spray on 18th and 25th DAP in V-1 mulberry revealed significantly highest growth parameters on 30th and 45th DAP viz., shoot height (17.11 and 55.63 cm), number of branches per plant (19.00 and 21.87 No.), number of leaves per plant (112.97 and

275.10 No.) and total leaf area (4940.26 and 26443.30 cm² / plant) with foliar application of 0.6 per cent nano nitrogen fertilizers on 25th DAP + 50 per cent nitrogen applied through soil. The leaf yield (704.64 and 928.53 g / plant on 45th and 60th DAP, respectively) was maximum in the mulberry leaves sprayed with 0.4 per cent nano nitrogen fertilizer on 25th DAP + 50 per cent soil application of nitrogen which supports the present study (Pooja *et al.*, 2022).

Table1: Effect of foliar application of different volumes of nanonitrogen fertilizer on Shoot length (cm) at various growth stages of V-1 mulberry

Treatments	30 DAP	45 DAP	60 DAP
T ₁ : Foliar application of 0.4 % nano N at 150 ltr per acre	41.43	81.33	127.63
T ₂ : Foliar application of 0.4 % nano N at 175 ltr per acre	42.64	82.68	131.33
T ₃ : Foliar application of 0.4 % nano N at 200 ltr per acre	43.46	84.46	141.21
T ₄ : Foliar application of 0.4 % nano N at 225ltr per acre	43.53	84.63	141.25
T ₅ : Foliar application of 2 % urea at 150 ltr per acre	39.61	77.25	121.53
T ₆ : Foliar application of 2 % urea at 175ltr per acre	40.65	78.68	122.11
T ₇ : Foliar application of 2 % urea at 200 ltr per acre	41.10	79.18	124.84
T ₈ : Foliar application of 2 % urea at 225 ltr per acre	41.25	80.05	129.74
T ₉ : control (Recommended PoP)	39.10	76.37	120.07
T ₁₀ : Absolute control	30.49	65.49	105.30
F-test	*	*	*
S.Em.±	0.022	0.617	1.357
CD@ 5%	0.066	1.833	4.032
CV	2.94	4.69	4.52

*Significant at 5 %, DAP: Days After Pruning, PoP: Package of Practice

Table2: Effect of foliar application of different volumes of nanonitrogen fertilizer on Number of branches per plant at different growth stages of V-1 mulberry

Treatments	30 DAP	45 DAP	60 DAP
T ₁ : Foliar application of 0.4 % nano N at 150 ltr per acre	18.47	19.97	21.12
T ₂ : Foliar application of 0.4 % nano N at 175 ltr per acre	18.58	20.00	21.61
T ₃ : Foliar application of 0.4 % nano N at 200 ltr per acre	18.97	20.77	22.28
T ₄ : Foliar application of 0.4 % nano N at 225ltr per acre	19.13	21.17	22.66
T ₅ : Foliar application of 2 % urea at 150 ltr per acre	16.83	17.73	19.21
T ₆ : Foliar application of 2 % urea at 175ltr per acre	17.63	17.70	19.39
T ₇ : Foliar application of 2 % urea at 200 ltr per acre	18.03	18.70	20.99
T ₈ : Foliar application of 2 % urea at 225 ltr per acre	18.10	19.37	21.29
T ₉ : control (Recommended PoP)	16.10	17.30	18.32
T ₁₀ : Absolute Control	14.73	14.83	15.70
F-test	*	*	*
S.Em.±	0.122	0.160	0.316
CD@ 5%	0.363	0.475	0.938
CV	5.15	4.32	4.49

*Significant at 5 %, DAP: Days After Pruning, PoP: Package of Practice

Table 3: Effect of foliar spray of different volumes of nano nitrogen fertilizer on number of leaves per mulberry plant at different days after pruning

Treatments	30 DAP	45 DAP	60 DAP
T ₁ : Foliar application of 0.4 % nano N at 150 ltr per acre	189.31	509.74	659.74
T ₂ : Foliar application of 0.4 % nano N at 175 ltr per acre	197.59	527.55	677.55
T ₃ : Foliar application of 0.4 % nano N at 200 ltr per acre	220.89	589.25	739.25
T ₄ : Foliar application of 0.4 % nano N at 225ltr per acre	226.73	602.83	752.83
T ₅ : Foliar application of 2 % urea at 150 ltr per acre	134.91	406.17	556.17
T ₆ : Foliar application of 2 % urea at 175ltr per acre	146.11	428.62	578.62
T ₇ : Foliar application of 2 % urea at 200 ltr per acre	164.50	460.53	610.53
T ₈ : Foliar application of 2 % urea at 225 ltr per acre	179.47	479.72	629.72
T ₉ : Control (Recommended PoP)	121.15	390.52	540.52
T ₁₀ : Absolute Control	96.87	234.90	354.90
F-test	*	*	*
S.Em.±	2.008	4.908	6.177
CD@ 5%	5.966	14.582	18.354
CV	5.15	5.32	5.10

*Significant at 5 %, DAP: Days After Pruning, PoP: Package of Practice

Table4 : Effect of foliar application of different volumes of nano nitrogen fertilizer On single leaf area (cm²) at various growth stages of V-1 mulberry

Treatments	Single leaf area (cm ²)		
	30 DAP	45 DAP	60 DAP
T ₁ : Foliar application of 0.4 % nano N at 150 ltr per acre	85.70	113.53	121.11
T ₂ : Foliar application of 0.4 % nano N at 175 ltr per acre	88.05	115.59	123.15
T ₃ : Foliar application of 0.4 % nano N at 200 ltr per acre	90.64	119.07	125.29
T ₄ : Foliar application of 0.4 % nano N at 225ltr per acre	90.78	119.81	126.40
T ₅ : Foliar application of 2 % urea at 150 ltr per acre	82.16	107.84	115.71
T ₆ : Foliar application of 2 % urea at 175ltr per acre	82.94	108.50	116.37
T ₇ : Foliar application of 2 % urea at 200 ltr per acre	83.92	111.23	119.21
T ₈ : Foliar application of 2 % urea at 225 ltr per acre	85.20	111.97	120.31
T ₉ : Control (Recommended PoP)	81.09	106.73	110.10
T ₁₀ : Absolute control	77.91	91.00	92.94
F-test	*	*	*
S.Em. ±	0.141	0.367	0.422
CD@ 5%	0.419	1.090	1.253
CV	3.84	5.14	4.79

*Significant at 5 %, DAP: Days After Pruning, PoP: Package of Practice

Table 5: Effect of foliar application of different volumes of nano nitrogen fertilizer on yield parameters of V-1 mulberry at 45th and 60th day after pruning

Treatments	Leaf yield (g/plant)		Leaf yield (kg/ha/crop)		Leaf yield (tonnes/ha/yr)	
	45DAP	60DAP	45DAP	60DAP	45DAP	60DAP
T ₁ : Foliar application of 0.4 % nano N at 150 ltr per acre	663.19	886.27	6140.43	8205.97	30.70	41.03
T ₂ : Foliar application of 0.4 % nano N at 175 ltr per acre	669.99	920.43	6203.44	8522.29	31.02	42.61
T ₃ : Foliar application of 0.4 % nano N at 200 ltr per acre	697.33	956.83	6456.55	8859.32	32.28	44.30
T ₄ : Foliar application of 0.4 % nano N at 225 ltr per acre	714.64	980.59	6616.82	9079.31	33.08	45.40
T ₅ : Foliar application of 2 % urea at 150 ltr per acre	517.95	804.88	4795.67	7452.41	23.98	37.26
T ₆ : Foliar application of 2 % urea at 175ltr per acre	530.33	837.97	4910.33	7758.80	24.55	38.79
T ₇ : Foliar application of 2 % urea at 200 ltr per acre	626.14	864.31	5797.43	8002.62	28.99	40.01
T ₈ : Foliar application of 2 % urea at 225 ltr per acre	635.09	867.07	5880.33	8028.19	29.40	40.14
T ₉ : Control (Recommended PoP)	530.33	799.48	4910.33	7402.39	24.55	37.01
T ₁₀ : Absolute control	372.14	482.55	3445.64	4467.90	17.23	22.34
F-test	*	*	*	*	*	*
S.Em.±	7.036	13.399	97.717	186.079	0.489	0.930
CD@ 5%	20.905	39.809	290.333	552.870	1.452	2.764
CV	4.18	5.11	5.14	4.82	5.28	5.11

*Significant at 5 %, DAP: Days After Pruning, PoP: Package of Practice

Conclusion

The treatments consisted of different volumes of nano nitrogen - fertilizer through foliar spray on 25th day after pruning. The maximum shoot height (43.53, 84.63 and 141.25 cm, respectively), number of branches per plant (19.13, 21.17 and 22.66, respectively), number of leaves per plant (226.73, 462.83 and 709.27, respectively) and single leaf area (90.78, 119.81 and 126.40 cm²), respectively on 30th, 45th and 60thDAP) were recorded in mulberry plants raised with foliar application of 0.4 per cent nano nitrogen fertilizers @ 225 ltr per acre with 50 per cent N through soil application (T₄).

The next pre-eminent treatment was 0.4 per cent nano nitrogen fertilizer @ 200 ltr per acre through foliar spray on 25th day after pruning + 50 per cent N through soil application (T₃) with shoot height of 43.46, 84.46 and 141.21 cm, respectively, number of branches per plant of 18.97, 20.77 and 22.28, respectively, number of leaves per plant of 220.89, 589.25 and 739.25, respectively and single leaf area of 90.64, 119.07 and 125.29 cm², respectively on 30th, 45th and 60th DAP. Whereas, lowest growth parameters were recorded in absolute control.

Among yield parameters maximum leaf yield per plant (714.64 and 980.59 g / plant, respectively on 45th and 60th day after pruning) was recorded in mulberry raised with application of 0.4 per cent nano nitrogen fertilizer @ 225 ltr per acre through foliar spray on 25th day after pruning + 50 per cent soil application of N, which was on par with foliar application of 0.4 per cent nano nitrogen fertilizers @ 200 ltr per acre on 25th day after pruning + 50 per cent soil application of N (T₃) (697.33 and 956.83 g / plant on 45th and 60th day after pruning, respectively). However, minimum leaf yield (372.14 and 482.55 g / plant, respectively on 45th and 60th day after pruning) was recorded in the absolute control plot.

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